

RE-IMAGINING COMMUNITY AND PLACE

NEW PERSPECTIVES ON INCLUSIVE
PARTICIPATORY APPROACHES
WITH OLDER ADULTS

Working Group 2: Community and Place

Participatory Approaches with Older Adults in context of Community and Place

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Executive Summary

This White Paper is a result of the collaborative efforts of members of Working Group 2 (WG2) „Community and Place” within the PAAR-net COST Action (CA22167). It examines the intersection of participatory approaches with diverse contexts and experiences of older adults. WG2 aims to bridge significant gaps in research and knowledge related to the varied ageing experiences across Europe and beyond. These gaps extend past general ageing issues to critical concerns such as social exclusion, marginalisation, cultural disadvantage, and ageism. The group addresses those by synthesising research and practical insights focused on older adults who tend to be excluded from participatory approaches, such as refugees, Indigenous people, migrants, those living in poverty or remote areas, and individuals with disabilities or cognitive and mental limitations.

The paper addresses both the challenges and opportunities of these approaches in community and place settings, providing actionable insights to enhance the inclusion of older adults in research, policy-making, and service design.

The challenges include:

- **Social exclusion and marginalisation:** Many older adults, particularly those from marginalised groups such as refugees, Indigenous people, migrants, and individuals living in poverty or remote areas, face significant barriers to participation. These impediments include cultural, social, and logistical obstacles that impede their engagement in participatory processes.
- **Cultural and socioeconomic disparities:** Participatory approaches must be culturally sensitive and adaptable to diverse worldviews, values, and needs of older adults. A lack of culturally tailored methods can result in ineffective engagement and limited impact.

- **Intersectionality and complexity:** Recognising how age, gender, ethnicity, and socioeconomic status intersect can lead to more nuanced and equitable solutions. Failure to consider these intersecting factors can lead to oversimplified solutions that do not fully address the issues.

The opportunities include:

- **Enhancing inclusivity:** Participatory approaches offer an opportunity to bridge significant gaps in research and knowledge by including diverse older adult groups in decision-making processes. Engaging a diverse range of older adults, particularly those from marginalised groups, leads to more inclusive and effective decision-making.
- **Establishing participatory approaches adapted to cultural diversity:** Developing culturally tailored participatory approaches that reflect unique worldviews, values, and needs of older adults in research, policy-making and service design
- **Strengthening local networks:** Local networks, including family, friends, and community institutions, play a crucial role in supporting the inclusion and well-being of older adults.
- **Developing tailored tools and methods:** The development and use of participatory tools and methods specifically designed to engage diverse groups of people can foster meaningful involvement. This customisation helps address the diverse needs of older adults and promotes more equitable and sufficient solutions.

In conclusion, the paper emphasises the urgent need for contextually sensitive and targeted research projects and actions to enhance participation among marginalised older demographic groups. It represents a resource for developing inclusive, effective, and evidence-based strategies that involve more diverse older populations in research, policy-making, and practice interventions across various communities and places.

1

INTRODUCTION

Background

This White Paper is the result of the collaborative work of the Working Group 2: Community and Place members. It provides an overview of leading research that explores policy challenges, equity issues and participatory approaches involving older adults from under-researched groups. WG2 addresses a well-documented gap in gerontological literature regarding the diverse experiences of the ageing population in Europe (Torres, 2015).

Although the diverse experiences of older adults are well documented, participatory approaches to involving them in research and decision-making are relatively new (Urbaniak & Wanka, 2023). In recent years, there has been a growing commitment from the research and scientific community to engage older adults with health, care, and support needs in research activities, in line with the European vision of “science for the people, by the people” (Horizon, the EU Research and Innovation magazine, April 2022). The dedication is reflected in increased efforts to frame policy-making across Europe to promote co-production and ensure that citizens, including older people, have a stronger voice and control over their lives (EU, 2023).

This White Paper emphasises the need for contextually sensitive, targeted positive action to enable participation among specific older population groups. The contribution serves as a resource for developing more inclusive, effective, and evidence-based approaches to involving diverse older populations in research and policy-making processes across European contexts.

Background

PAAR-net COST Action's WG2 focuses on the following specific older population groups:

- Older migrants and refugees (especially those without citizenship).
- Indigenous peoples (such as e.g. the Māori in New Zealand, the Sami in Sweden, and Travellers in Ireland)
- Older adults who lack access to adequate infrastructure (including those from remote or deprived areas, living in poor conditions, or experiencing homelessness).

This WG responds directly to the challenge of inclusion in participatory research, namely to counter prevailing ageist prejudices that cast the older population in Europe as a homogenous group and the persistent ageist narrative that characterises older adults as associated with burden, decline, and care needs (Walsh et al., 2017). Consistent empirical evidence shows that these ageist stereotypes affect the perception of older people by society and their treatment in social spaces, including in health care and support service settings (Stephens, 2018; Fraser et al., 2020).

This paper synthesises findings from various research activities aimed at maximising the inclusivity and applicability of participatory methodologies (Abma et al., 2019) to support research and practice addressing inequalities and reflecting the diverse experiences of ageing societies.

Purpose and Scope

This document presents the outcomes of systematic dialogues and written communications among members of Working Group 2 (WG2), which collectively aim to address the following questions:

- ➔ What do we already know about involving older migrants and refugees (especially those without citizenship), Indigenous people, and those older adults who lack access to adequate infrastructure in research, practice interventions and policy making? What can we learn from experiences across different jurisdictions, and where are the knowledge gaps?
- ➔ How can we improve existing approaches to involving older adults in these domains in research, practice interventions, and policymaking by maximising their applicability and inclusiveness in a more innovative way?
- ➔ How can the involvement of older adults as co-researchers enhance the quality of research, practice interventions and improve policy development?

The findings presented consider participatory research within specific cultural and sociopolitical contexts and their applicability to certain groups of older people. In doing so, this document highlights fundamental debates relating to inclusive community-based participatory research (Banks et al., 2013 & Waldegrave et al., 2023), including the importance of researcher reflexivity (Groot et al., 2022; Groot et al., 2019; Urbaniak 2023) and addressing issues of power imbalance (Banks et al., 2013; Waldegrave et al. 2023).

Nevertheless, we need to note that these findings have been contextualised within specific local and regional frameworks. That underscores a fundamental tenet in participatory gerontological research: the significant influence of local, regional, and national systems on the methodologies and implementation of participatory initiatives involving older adults. Consequently, this precludes a one-size-fits-all approach (Lamura & Nies, 2024).

The evidence findings presented here advocate for a transition from rigid participatory paradigms towards more flexible approaches that account for local and national distinctiveness while responding to both individual and structural pressures. Contextual sensitivity and awareness emerge as a key feature and a core principle in PAAR-net COST Action (CA22167) methodology, evidence-based recommendations and overall approach.

CHALLENGES STATEMENT

Participatory approaches in research, development projects and policy programmes aim to involve individuals in knowledge production and decision-making processes that affect their lives, promoting inclusivity and empowerment (Urbaniak and Wanka, 2023). However, several challenges can hinder older adults' effective participation and co-creation.

Critical concerns have emerged regarding power differences, communication dynamics and a lack of skills and resources (Buffel, 2018; Corrado et al., 2020; Tanner, 2019). Furthermore, Mey and Van Hoven (2019, pp. 332–333) identify three themes in need of further examination:

- ➔ co-researcher empowerment,
- ➔ production of a “knowledge,”
- ➔ resource investment.

Understanding older adults' needs and preferences in different cultural and regional contexts is vital when designing and executing participatory projects effectively. This section addresses the challenges of applying participatory approaches in Bosnia Herzegovina as an example. It focuses on issues, such as the variation in cultural norms, historical backgrounds, and social and political dynamics. Moreover, the impact of different jurisdictional policies and regulations can create barriers to effective engagement. These complexities are explored further through the case of a Roma community in Northwest Romania, where the environmental justice issues underscore the difficulties of engaging marginalised groups in decision-making processes.

Examining these varied experiences allows us to shed light on the specific challenges faced in different cultural and legal environments. Understanding these factors is crucial for developing strategies that adapt and respond to the unique needs and contexts of older adults in various communities and jurisdictions.

Participatory Approaches Beyond the Mainstream: Challenges in Reaching Marginalised Older Adults

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The research for the study *Ageing in the Urban Context: Evidence from Sarajevo* has helped highlight the complexity of retired citizens' social status in contemporary Bosnian society (Emirhafizović & Šadić, 2018). Given the demographic profile of Sarajevo Canton and the ongoing trend of population ageing, the number of individuals in this age group has been steadily increasing. According to the latest available official estimates from 2022, people aged 65 and older make up nearly 18% of the total population in Sarajevo Canton (Federalni zavod za statistiku [FZS] – Federal Institute of Statistics of Bosnia, 2023).

The heterogeneity of this group is influenced by both personal biographies and structural factors, which further impact their level of social participation. Due to the war in Bosnia and Herzegovina in the 1990s (1992–1995), there was significant population displacement within the country's borders and out-migration, largely driven by ethnic cleansing. During this period, for security and other reasons, many citizens left Sarajevo, which was under a four-year siege. At the same time, forcibly displaced persons, mainly from smaller towns and rural areas, particularly from Eastern Bosnia, were arriving in the city. These large-scale population fluctuations brought urban and rural ways of life into coexistence, inevitably reflecting differences across nearly all domains. Refugees, primarily from smaller towns and rural areas, particularly from Eastern Bosnia, were arriving in the city. Such large-scale population fluctuations brought urban and rural ways of life into coexistence, inevitably reflecting differences across nearly all domains.

Different cultural patterns in urban and rural areas imply specific family relationships and often diverse value systems. This issue has a pronounced gender connotation. From a Life Course perspective, women's employment and education in the city during socialism largely determined the quality of their lives at a later age. This was usually not the case for less educated women from rural areas, who tended to be more oriented towards home and family. While this latter orientation may reduce feelings of loneliness, it can also result in spending much of their time confined within the „four walls“ of their homes in an urban situation. As a consequence, these two subgroups, although geographically close, actually live in parallel realities. There is a clear challenge in reaching isolated, discouraged or marginalised older adults who, unlike their counterparts, are not involved in social activities or part of existing networks in local communities or municipalities.

Additional reasons for neglecting older adults in Sarajevo Canton include government instability and the prioritisation of other areas and population groups (e.g., youth) in financial resource allocation. These matters have not been adequately addressed in the past. Dominant media narratives about older adults often focus on retirement payment costs and the challenges of maintaining healthcare services, similar to trends in many other countries. As a result, policy measures that could turn Sarajevo into a more age-friendly city (concept proposed by WHO in 2007) are not considered, even though good initiatives emerge in various sectors of society.

These challenges also apply to another relatively numerous but underrepresented group: the Roma population in Bosnia and Herzegovina, who are disproportionately affected by poverty, social exclusion, systematic discrimination, and ghettoization. These structural disadvantages faced by the Roma have a transgenerational character, leading mainstream society to often perceive them as inherent to the group in a discriminatory manner (cf. Institution of Human Rights Ombudsman of Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2012; UNICEF, 2013).

Environmental Justice for Marginalised Communities: Bridging the Gap Between Marginalised Communities and Decision-Makers

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As in the case above, a study focusing on the Roma community living in and around a rubbish dump in north-western Romania revealed various injustices. They posed as a cultural minority living under conditions of rejection by the rest of society, and the status quo was perpetuated (Petrescu-Mag et al., 2016). The qualitative approach adopted in the study aimed to answer the question of “To what extent can environmental justice be provided to those targeted?”. The study revised the three following action options:

- on-site living opportunities—which was eventually preferred,
- off-site living opportunities,
- do nothing.

The analysis concludes that we should adopt a nuanced approach, allowing flexibility in implementation and respecting equity and participation. However, there have been significant challenges in engaging the affected community and decision-makers due to geographic, historical and cultural factors and entrenched political interests.

OPPORTUNITIES

Engaging participatory approaches with older adults offers unique opportunities to enhance research and service design, particularly in addressing issues like vulnerability and loneliness in later life. According to Buffel (2018), co-production is a sound working method for accessing the expertise and knowledge of older adults. By involving older populations in research, development projects and policy programmes, it is possible to incorporate views of unheard populations and provide a platform for meaningful social engagement, support and mutual learning (Buffel 2018).

Furthermore, participatory approaches can help bridge generational and cultural gaps, fostering mutual understanding and respect between different people groups. In this section, we reflect on the opportunities that participatory approaches present, highlighting experiences and strategies that have led to meaningful engagement and positive outcomes. The section consists of four parts written by members of WG2 from the different cultural perspectives of Estonia (Tiina Tambaum), France (Damien Vanneste) and Portugal (Mário Rui André) that will exemplify the benefits of involving older adults as active contributors rather than mere participants of the research process.

All four texts underscore the importance of including older adults in participatory research and decision-making processes. Older adults' contributions not only enhance the relevance and effectiveness of the outcomes but also foster a sense of shared purpose and community. By listening and responding to the unique perspectives of older adults, we can develop more inclusive and responsive services and policies that better address the needs of their and other age groups.

Developing a Cognitively Stimulating Phone Befriending Service

– A Participatory Research Approach

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Fudge and associates (2007) have pointed out that the evaluation of participatory research has been focused on the influence on participants rather than on the impact on research processes and outcomes. The current project was designed to compare the respective results of the younger and older co-developers in a service design.

Implementation

In 2020–2021, research was conducted in Estonia, aiming to develop conversation topics through regular phone calls (phone befriending) (Cattan et al., 2008) in a way that offered a cognitive challenge to each call recipient. In this phone befriending, all the call recipients were older persons. The call providers consisted of older, middle-aged and younger volunteers. The point of having both older and younger call providers was to highlight any substantive differences between people with shorter and longer life experiences in the phone befriending service for older adults.

The researcher found 12 call providers (CP) through a media campaign and separate consultations. Then, every CP connected with their call receiver (CR), who was retired and preferably in social isolation. The CP/CR-pairs conducted phone befriending regularly once a week for 3 months. CPs tested the content and reported the results immediately after every call via the web-based questionnaire.

Besides the immediate feedback, the authors organised three focus groups among CPs during the research. The main discussion themes in the focus groups centred on the experiences of the phone befriending conversations and their impacts on the relationship with CRs. As a result of the focus group discussions, the content of the following calls was modified. At the end of the 3-month testing, the CPs completed their final feedback and task and themes evaluation applied during the research. They also provided suggestions for further development of the research methodology. Alongside these tasks, the participants held a final deliberative dialogue with the older participants to obtain feedback from their research participation experience.

Benefits

The research emphasised the nuances in the service that would not have been possible without older people's involvement in both the recipient and provider aspects. The importance of the older adults' inclusion as CPs in the phone befriending service development was noted through their shared coexistence (survivorship) as older people with the CRs, in turn, may have provided a chance to achieve a better balance in the interaction. The advantage of a peer might also have helped avoid the phenomenon often characterising the younger participants – making less adequate assumptions about the choice of material in advance. The study showed that the older participants could mediate the experience better from the perspective of both the service providers and the end users.

YOLD – YOunger-oLDer Committee at the Municipal Government: Participatory Approach in Action Research

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Tallinn University, Estonia

For nine months (2022/23), the younger and older people's committee (YOLD – YOung-oLD) worked experimentally at the Tartu municipal government (Estonia). The YOLD included five members between 16 and 19 years old, and five aged 65+. All participants, including older persons, participated as co-creators of the new type of citizen-governance interaction and community development.

The project aimed to:

- Test the YOLD-type committee as an alternative form for older people's involvement in decision-making processes and intergenerational cooperation in the municipality.
- Describe the processes of finding motivated members, functions, forms, work processes, and risks of YOLD.

Whether a study can be considered participatory research, rather than just an approach, interview, or observation as a source of data for researchers, depends on several conditions. These include whether local stakeholders can perceive themselves as co-creators and decision-makers, or the type of creative and qualitative methods implemented (Fang et al., 2018). In the present study, older participants were invited to be on a committee operating in their municipality, but they were also aware of their influence on the structure and rules of similar committees operating in other municipalities in the future. Thus, besides the research methods implemented by academic researchers, co-creation methods, including researcher diaries, interviews with the head of YOLD, official communication monitoring and document analysis, were also employed. Moreover, the project utilized interviews and observations in which senior participants could participate.

During the nine months, the YOLD committee delivered feedback to the municipal government and suggested ways to improve the quality of life of young people and pensioners. Furthermore, it allowed for the improvement of intergenerational contacts and meaningful cooperation in the municipality. Simultaneously, the researchers determined the problems and barriers faced by YOLD members and identified success and failure factors in work processes and communication patterns. The older volunteers were not trained in advance for their new roles in YOLD. The feedback obtained by the researchers enabled them to develop structure and content for future YOLD participants. The experiment revealed details impossible to uncover without the older co-facilitators.

Benefits

Many of the results were obtained through the co-creators' involvement:

- The YOLD format contributed to the involvement of older people in decision-making processes, as they were specifically motivated by intergenerational cooperation.
- It uncovered an individualized but broad-based approach to member search.
- It relied on potential members being invited personally by referrals (increasing personal motivation level) or at the suggestion of a group of peers (ensuring a democratic process). That included representation of the passive old, able-bodied, people with disabilities, „young old” and „old old”, etc.

The YOLD topics do not have to be age-related. YOLD provides an opportunity to create a participatory culture.

Participatory Approach as a Mean to Involve Policymakers in the Issue of Ageing

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Local participatory programs in France tend to be the initiative of local councillors. This is the case in many age-friendly cities and communities. As for the “ageing in place” issue — as a local policy issue — there are significant differences in the involvement levels from area to area. These variations do not relate to the higher or lower relevance of the ageing matter. They may be explained by the diversity of political sensitivity and the perception (or lack thereof) of the issue itself.

My colleague Hugo Bertillot and I, together with an association from the north of France (called: Debout les aîné-e-s), attempted to initiate local mobilisation (especially political mobilisation) on this issue. To do so we set up and led, together with four members of Debout les aîné-e-s, a participatory research project in a disadvantaged commune in the north of France (a small town of 5,000 inhabitants in a former mining basin, which has not initiated any process related to “adapting society to ageing”). We chose the “citizen design” method created by Marion Scheider-Yilmaz and Jean-Philippe Viriot-Durandal (REIACTIS). The method was used during six meetings with a group of senior citizens (an average of 15 to 20 people) to set up an area diagnosis, identify priorities for activities formalised in “action sheets”, and present these action lines at a public event, inviting public decision-makers.

Due to the initial difficulties in contacting local representatives, we decided to start our project by creating a group of senior citizens interested in joining such a project. We were able to do this with the help of local associations acting as intermediaries, as well as through word of mouth. The group had six to eight members at the first meetings, and by the end, it grew to over 25 participants.

We should note that the project's start caught the attention of several local councillors. One local councillor met with the group at the start of the project and provided a more user-friendly room. Moreover, as the participatory dynamic broadened, the citizen design team could eventually meet with the mayor. The mayor was surprised at the group's progress but expressed support for the future. He made a village hall available for the public presentation. He also helped to draw up the guest list for the event, meaning that elected representatives on other levels of government (*Communauté de communes, Département, Région, etc.*) concerned with the challenges of ageing in their areas could attend as well.

Benefits

The research and action project took place over six months in collaboration with the *Debout les aîné-e-s* association. It ran with a group of older adults from the commune in northern France between November 2023 and April 2024. It is too early to determine whether the specific measures proposed by this group would be implemented.

Yet what has already been established is the growing awareness of ageing as a global issue, not only in terms of health but also social connectedness, living environment, services, etc. Alongside the many benefits of the participatory approach in terms of results, we can also point to its ability to indirectly mobilise political players who were initially uninterested in some issues and to transform political cultures.

Implementation

Political support tends to be viewed as a prerequisite for establishing a participatory approach likely to have an impact. Nevertheless, this support does not exist in some areas right from the outset. Sometimes, this is due to opposition, often indifference. In such cases, evidence-based discourse is insufficient in convincing political partners to engage.

Therefore, ongoing activities involving an increasing number of stakeholders can prove effective means to gradually gain the support of local elected representatives without being overly formal. That enables them to become aware of the civic capacity of older people in their community as they move forward and discover the cross-cutting nature of ageing issues in their area.

Promoting Participatory Approaches with Older Citizens

Mário Rui André,

Santa Casa da Misericórdia de Lisboa, Portugal

Engaging citizens in public policy design and development is increasingly recognised as valuable for enhancing interactions between individuals, organisations, and government at various levels (local, regional, and national). Such an approach acknowledges that citizens, including older adults, have valuable insights into community issues and can contribute effectively to developing practical solutions that address local needs, leveraging their skills and experiences.

Promoting citizen participation aspires to improve the decision-making process by incorporating diverse perspectives, which can lead to more suitable and efficient solutions to societal challenges. In this context, participation is not solely perceived as a means to improve the democratic process but also as a beneficial contribution to the social innovation process (Age Platform Europe, 2014), aiming for more effective solutions for community issues, such as age-related ones.

The urge for older people's participation also stems from the view that older people are often the object of neglect and marginalisation and can find themselves in a situation of social vulnerability, whether for socioeconomic or cultural reasons or for reasons of a loss of autonomy and mobility (Fernandes, 1997).

The older people's participation in decision-making processes related to the promotion of ageing in the community – apart from improving their physical and psychological well-being (autonomy, self-acceptance, self-esteem, locus of control) – can also significantly influence the change in social roles attributed to older people in the community context (Fonseca, 2005). In this sense, specific initiatives have been advocated for the involvement of older people in community governance processes through individual participation and their involvement in local organisations and associations (Östlund, 2015).

Although promoting the participation and involvement of local actors must consider the specific characteristics of the territories, some general principles and actions can be identified that should be taken into account. Those include the following.

At the citizen level:

- Guarantee citizen participation in all phases of integrated governance processes and not just in the consultation and public consultation phases or simple information about the decisions taken,
- Citizen involvement and participation must be proactive and implicit throughout the strategic planning of integrated governance processes,
- Seek to improve individual abilities to participate in integrated collaborative processes to promote ageing in the community,
- Correct imbalances and inequities in participation among citizens, in particular, those most vulnerable for socioeconomic, cultural or educational reasons,
- Combat discrimination and prejudice that may exist in relation to low expectations of participation and involvement of older citizens in the decision-making process,
- Plan the creation and development of local mechanisms and instruments that promote the informed participation of citizens (advocacy and information, community forums, training, events, workshops, focus groups, panels of opinion leaders, public consultation, participatory budgeting, pilot experiences, social networks, advertising campaigns etc.).

At the organisational agents' level:

- The involvement and participation of local organisational actors must be of intersectoral representation and appropriate to the approach to promoting ageing in the community,
- Ensure the participation of local organisational actors who can get involved in the co-construction of collaborative processes to promote ageing in the community,
- Explore with organisational actors the risks/benefits of their involvement, to clarify myths, and prejudices and overcome obstacles to participation in integrated collaborative processes,
- Support the development of organisational and departmental cultures open to citizen participation and involvement in decision-making processes,
- Specific training and training for professionals on the importance and strategies for promoting citizen participation and involvement in decision-making processes, thus contributing to the development of organisational cultures.

4

CASE STUDIES

In this section, we present a collection of case studies by the PAAR-net COST Action's WG2 members and explore various initiatives that emphasise the active participation of older adults in research, policy-making, and community activities. Involving diverse groups and focusing on culturally relevant methods allowed us to demonstrate how inclusive practices can lead to more effective and meaningful outcomes and help us to reimagine older adults' participation and social inclusion.

The first case study by Charles Waldegrave highlights the development of culturally relevant well-being measures for Māori Elders in New Zealand. Through co-creation and participatory methods, this research ensures that Māori values would be considered in policy-making and service provision. Then, Ute Karl and Anne Ramos examine the social support networks of older migrants in Luxembourg. This case study emphasises the crucial role of neighbours, friends, and institutional care in overcoming language barriers and cultural differences to improve well-being. Finally, Marion Scheider-Yilmaz presents a participatory method to involve diverse older adult profiles in local decision-making in France. The study demonstrates how targeted approaches can effectively bring marginalised voices into the process, ensuring that the perspectives of older migrants, women, and individuals with disabilities are heard.

Together, these case studies illustrate the transformative potential of participatory approaches and community involvement in enhancing the well-being of older adults. By prioritising inclusivity and cultural relevance, these case examples offer valuable insights into creating supportive environments for ageing populations.

Case Study 1: Participatory Approaches with Indigenous Communities to Improve Policy Responses

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(The Family Centre Social Policy Research Unit, Lower Hutt, Wellington, New Zealand)

Objective

This research aims to provide co-created qualitative and quantitative information on kaumātua (Māori Elders Indigenous to New Zealand) well-being and participation in culturally appropriate policy formation, environmental planning and culturally responsive services. The presentation aimed to outline the aspects of the research carried out to develop authentic kaumātua socio-economic measures (and scales) through co-creation gatherings designed to overcome Western assumption bias and centrally focussed on Māori values and notions of well-being. It is part of a broader study entitled “Tai Kaumātutanga Older Māori Well-being and Participation: Present and Future Focus”, funded by the Ageing Well National Science Challenge in New Zealand.

The purpose of developing culturally based social measures was because the current indicator scales used to provide evidence for policy-making and developing services are Western and ceased to reflect key aspects of Māori values (Waldegrave et al., 2023). While some loneliness, discrimination, and social bonding characteristics tend to be universal, others are culture-specific.

Older Māori value spirituality, collective thinking and activities, and the primary value of genealogical connections, contrasting with the Western focus on secularism, individualism and nuclear family structures. Western scales naturally reflect the cultures out of which they emerged, so the evidence they provide for policy-making, for example, is appropriate for Western societies. However, it does not take into account the unique Māori aspects of loneliness, well-being, or even discrimination. If the evidence is not apprehended, decision-makers and those who design services often simply focus on the evidence at hand, and the unique cultural aspects tend to be overlooked. That may explain why outcomes for non-Western groups, and particularly Indigenous people, are frequently less successful than for mainstream Western groups.

Methodology

A qualitative co-creation methodology with older Māori was used to construct an Older Māori Well-being indicator scale that reflected their world views and experiences. That is one of six indicators under development. The other scales focus on loneliness, social connection, discrimination, abuse, and neighbourhood well-being.

Co-creation hui (meetings) with Older Māori took place throughout Aotearoa (Māori word for New Zealand) with eight different groups of older Māori. These were led by Māori researchers being members of the study team. The hui were participatory and occurred in a Māori way expressing their values and ways of doing things (Waldegrave and Mercury, 2023).

Every group included:

- *Karakia and mihi* (blessing and welcome speech),
- *Waiata tautoko* (support song),
- *Mihimihi Whakawhanaungatanga* (introductions about who you are),
- *Manaakitanga* (hospitality),
- *Hui Kōrero* – (promoting and encouraging open dialogue),
- *Wānanga Kōrero* – (gathering of ideas and mātauranga (knowledge) – recorded with consent),
- *Poroporoaki* (closing thoughts, reflection, and thanks),
- *Koha* (a gift for their time),
- *Waiata and karakia ano* (song and blessing).

The Kaupapa, or focus, of the hui was about well-being and quality of life. Participants were invited to share about happiness and security providing them a quality of life or well-being. They were invited to share the key things that gave them happiness as older Māori. What makes them and other Māori their age, or older feel secure and comfortable? What reduces their happiness? What are the things that make them feel insecure and uncomfortable? What gives them and other older Māori friends and relatives a sense of fulfilment? The responses were recorded (with permission) and themed. The primary themes were developed into questions to create an initial Older Māori Wellbeing Scale.

The co-created Older Māori Wellbeing Scale, along with the other similarly constructed social scales referred to above, were then placed in a questionnaire administered to a national random sample of 2,000 plus Māori 50 years and over. In the result analysis, we could test the scales for statistical reliability and validity. Thus, a participatory piece of co-created research was able to be tested using quantitative methods regarding its fitness to be used as an indicator scale, in this case, a well-being scale.

Findings

The co-constructed responses were categorised into themes. The 12 statements reflecting the most recurring themes compiled for the well-being scale – the qualitative findings of the study.

Three examples of the 12 statements that emerged in the analysis include:

→ **I am well-connected to Te Ao Māori (the Māori world).**

Strongly agree/Agree/Disagree/Strongly disagree

→ **I enjoy a wairua (spiritual) connection in my life.**

Strongly agree/Agree/Disagree/Strongly disagree

→ **I feel respected and able to contribute to the well-being of my whānau (extended family) and community.**

Often/Sometimes/Not often/Never

The 12 statements in the co-created Older Māori Wellbeing Scale undergone testing for reliability and validity in a survey on a national random sample of 2,000+ older Māori. The results showed high scores, considerably above the threshold, using Cronbach's Alpha, when testing for internal consistency and reliability (a score of 0.843 for the 12 queries). The Confirmatory Factor Analysis scores were also strong. Using the R package lavaan. All but two questions had a factor loading score well above 0.4, seven questions were above 0.5 and three well above 0.7, demonstrating the validity of the scales.

Significance

The significance of this research is that it has developed an innovative methodology to draw on the knowledge of the people for whom the scales were created to devise tools that can be used for evidence in policy-making and service provision for their people. Developing social indicators co-created with these communities, incorporating their knowledge and experience of life quality in their communities, offers more tangible evidence for inclusive policy-making and service delivery. The standard international scale covers universal aspects of loneliness but not significant culturally specific aspects.

Case Study 2: Ageing as a Migrant. Support Networks and Care in (Dependent) Old Age

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Background

Research involving older migrants tends to focus on the importance of family members in the exchange of support, emphasising the care practices exchanged between generations. Little attention is paid to other types of social relationships relevant to the well-being of older migrants, especially after retirement and if they require institutional care. The project “*Biographies and (trans)national Social Support Networks of older migrants in Luxembourg*” (2013-2016, University of Luxembourg, financed by the University of Luxembourg) addressed this research gap through analysing the social support networks of older migrants in Luxembourg.

Objectives

The overall objectives of this project were:

- to provide deep insights into the biographical patterns of older migrants and to reconstruct the relation between life courses and circumstances of life in later life.
- to reconstruct the meanings of social relations and social networks under a transnational perspective.
- to give insights into the social support systems of older migrants and the forms of provided care.

Methodology

The project involved 34 migrants from Belgium, France, Germany, Portugal, and Italy, 10 of whom received some form of regular institutional care (by mobile care services, daycare centres, or care homes).

The research plan was to interview older migrants twice, using biographical and egocentric network interviews. Biographical and narrative interviews offer the possibility to understand the constructions of past time from today's point of view, to understand current ways of living, to explore the agency individuals have, to grasp the development of networks over time and to understand individual perspectives for the future. Qualitative social network analysis offers the possibility to systematically describe the quality and meaning of social relations, the different groups or communities people belong to, and the types of social support offered or received. The combination of both methods makes it possible to shed light on the changes in personal relations throughout life and to show how different social structures and social categories are relevant to the development of social relations.

Although the project was not originally conceived as a participatory project, the research team took several actions during the project that changed the degree of participation of the people involved, such as:

We did not just want to interview older migrants to gather information about their lives. Instead of asking only the questions we had defined in our interview guide (and that were important to us as researchers), we primarily and foremost listened to what the older migrants wanted to tell us, i.e., what they thought was and were important in their lives.

In this sense, the meetings with the people interviewed often happened several times. The researcher was invited to visit their homes, vegetable gardens or even the institutional unit where the spouse with dementia was spending the day (couple living together in a care home) to understand the meaning these places have for them; to see photo albums of different transnational family members, to participate in community gatherings, such as the sardine and chestnut festival, to celebrate with them and to experience the importance of social community and companionship, and to cook together, to understand the meaning of some kinds of food and the challenge to eat institutional meals provided by care institutions.

At the end of the project, the researchers also discussed the results with some participants, gathered their impressions about the analysis, and reanalysed and rediscussed some key aspects. Sometimes the findings' priority order changed, other times, the analysis was fully validated and became even more relevant. These perspectives were incorporated into the project results, and findings were (re-)formulated where necessary.

The project plan included a workshop with researchers, stakeholders, policy-makers, some project participants, and other older migrants likely to be interested in the topic. This way, they could not only see the outcomes of the project but also raise other points that they consider relevant. What we heard from them after the workshop was that their participation in the project resonated where it belonged (i.e., with those involved in practice and social policy development), that they felt they had a chance to have their say, and that this represented a hope that the situation could improve in the future.

The project brochure was written in French and German so that it could be understood by the whole population. It was sent to policy-makers, stakeholders, interest groups, and all participants wishing to receive it. We wanted to change the view that participants only take part in data collection and are very often not involved in the process of data processing, or the results of the project.

Findings

1. Family is very important to older migrants. It is one of the reasons why they did/do not return to their home countries during retirement. Yet, there are also other social contacts vital in their everyday lives. These include:

- ➔ **Neighbours** – they provide daily practical care, as children are often busy with work and do not live nearby,
- ➔ **Friends/Acquaintances in the designation country** – they provide companionship and emotional support after retirement, as they go through similar issues and challenges when retiring as “an older migrant”. Moreover, as many of them worked long shifts to save as much money as possible to bring back, they did not have many opportunities to form friendships during their professional life. Therefore, such friendships are often formed through institutional/cultural programmes.

2. The people interviewed did not expect their children to provide them with direct personal, physical care. Therefore, all forms of institutional care become important in a dependent old age. While the care provided is rated very highly by both non-dependent and dependent older migrants, there are concerns about the quality of social interactions. Three main factors appear to be vital include:

- Language barriers,
- Perceived cultural differences,
- Tension between the needs of older people and institutional rules for professionals.

As older migrants are still a minority in care facilities and very often do not speak Luxembourgish, they are often socially isolated in care institutions. Significant social interactions usually take place when they have the opportunity to meet institutional workers (e.g. cleaning, kitchen or driving staff) who speak the same language as them. However, as these people are working, these interactions are usually brief.

In addition, older migrants who are cared for at home feel isolated because professional caregivers are almost the only social contact they have in their daily lives. However, caregivers have busy schedules and are asked not to interact too much with their patients to avoid emotional dependency.

Policy Recommendations

Socialising with friends and acquaintances in cultural activities proves to be significant for some migrants who enjoy these kinds of activities. Although it is not for everyone, many of the older migrants we interviewed emphasised the importance of this type of social contact in their well-being. Given this, it would be interesting to create even more opportunities across the country to link with migrants through shared interests. Older migrants should be consulted about activities they find useful.

Migrants who do not speak Luxembourgish could benefit from institutional contexts aware of the language barriers and cultural needs of the older population – in our case, those coming from Italy and Portugal, who mainly learn French in Luxembourg and not Luxembourgish or German.

It would be advantageous in a multilingual country such as Luxembourg for (professional) care workers and other staff in institutional settings to speak the same language as older migrants. Aligning the language competencies of both care providers and care receivers poses a big opportunity for both sides.

Important Remarks Concerning More Participatory Approaches

Despite the project not being conceived as a participatory project, it was clear that using a more participative approach not only changed the way we designed it but also yielded the following results:

- It enabled the researchers to gain a better understanding of the (daily) lives of older migrants,
- It allowed a new perception of the data once the outcomes were discussed with some participants,
- It provided a new perspective on participation in the research project, as some older migrants felt that their participation had a purpose when they were invited to the project workshop to be seated with stakeholders and decision-makers. It was the first visit to the university for many of them.

However, we did not have the same opportunities (due to a lack of resources and mobility) as those receiving regular professional care, raising the question of how to enable participation for those living in care facilities.

Case Study 3: Social Inclusion of Older Adults at a Glance. Citizen Design – a Participatory Research Project with Older Adults

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Background

Nowadays, a broad range of participatory approaches and research projects involving older people continue to develop in France and other countries. While the inclusion of older adults in research and projects directly concerning them has become a common goal, there is often insufficient attention to involving diverse groups and profiles. Consequently, participatory approaches tend to engage very homogeneous groups, thereby perpetuating the invisibility of others (e.g., older migrants, older women, and older adults with disabilities).

Objective

This research project aims to develop a participatory method involving a variety of older adult profiles in local decision-making processes. Initially, the prototype of the method has been tested in one experimental location (T1) and is then further tested in eight additional locations across France by a pool of researchers (T2). The method is eventually assessed by the involved researchers using a common assessment framework and translated into a toolkit.

Research Questions

The research revolved around the following questions:

- Do the outcomes of the participatory process differ based on the groups of older people involved?
- Does shaping a method targeting the most excluded groups of older adults lead to greater inclusiveness in participatory research and, ultimately, in the decision-making process?

Methods

The research project involves the participatory method development and testing. The participants design and present concrete solutions to key local players and decision-makers. The two formed groups constituted:

- one with older adults highly involved in social and civic activities,
- the other with older adults who are usually less or not involved in such activities.

The approach utilises many inclusive tools to help the groups conduct a local diagnostic and develop solutions to the identified problems. The method has then been detailed in a toolkit and replicated by different research teams throughout France.

Preliminary Findings Overview

Diverse participation leads to various outcomes

The preliminary testing of the participatory method indicates that the outcomes of the participatory process vary significantly based on the diversity of the older adult groups involved. Groups with different backgrounds and levels of involvement in social and civic activities provide distinct perspectives and solutions, highlighting the importance of inclusivity in participatory research.

Enhanced inclusiveness through targeted methods

The method designed to include the most excluded groups of older adults – such as older migrants, older women, and older adults with disabilities – demonstrates a better level of inclusiveness in both the research process and the decision-making outcomes. This targeted approach effectively brings marginalised voices into local decision-making processes.

Effective use of inclusive tools and tips

The inclusive tools employed in the participatory method have proven effective in enabling older adults to conduct local diagnostics and develop concrete solutions. These tools facilitate engagement and ensure that all participants, regardless of their previous civic involvement rate, can contribute meaningfully to the project.

Scalability and replicability of the method

The successful replication of the participatory method in multiple locations across France suggests that the method is scalable and adapts to different contexts. The common assessment framework and toolkit developed through this research provide a standardised approach that can be utilised by various research teams, ensuring consistent cross-analysis of the local results.

Reflection

The findings of this research project underscore the critical importance of diversity and inclusivity in participatory approaches involving older adults. Actively striving to include a variety of older adult profiles (especially those often marginalised), the project enriches the decision-making process with diverse perspectives and ensures the typically unheard voices are amplified. The success of the inclusive tools and methods in engaging participants of varying backgrounds and civic involvement levels highlights the potential for these approaches to be adapted and scaled across different contexts.

CONCLUSION

The projects and discussions presented in this white paper underscore the critical importance of participatory approaches and community involvement in enhancing the well-being, inclusion and social integration of older adults.

The following several key preliminary conclusions arise from the WG2's collaborative efforts.

Cultural Relevance and Inclusivity

The discussions and research projects presented in this White Paper underscore the importance of developing culturally relevant frameworks and methodologies that align with the values and specific experiences of various communities. For instance, in the first case study, Waldegrave demonstrates the necessity of incorporating Indigenous values and perspectives into policy-making and service provision. It highlights the most effective policies and programmes, resonating with the cultural identities of the people they aim to serve. The culturally diverse practice inclusion ensures that older adults from different backgrounds are heard and fosters a sense of belonging and respect for their traditions and ways of life. It becomes particularly relevant when addressing the needs of migrant and minority populations. Future research projects and initiatives should emphasise the rich significance of cultural values and perspectives many marginalised people have to reflect the diversity of ageing populations globally.

Local Networks' Support

The work of WG2 members illustrates the critical role of local networks - comprising family, friends, neighbours, and community institutions - in supporting older adults' well-being and social inclusion. These informal and formal networks create a safety net, enhancing physical and emotional well-being, especially for people in vulnerable or marginalised circumstances. Attention should be paid to particular attention to addressing language barriers, cultural differences, and social isolation, especially when working with migrant populations, individuals from minority backgrounds or people experiencing physical or mental limitations. That should include supportive policies and well-funded service provision.

Diverse Experiences of Ageing in Place

Ageing in place – the ability for individuals to remain in their homes and communities as they grow older – is an increasingly recognised goal for promoting well-being among older adults. This concept is particularly significant as it reflects a preference for familiar environments and a more all-around social need for communities to adapt to the evolving requirements of ageing populations. However, it is essential to recognize that the experiences of ageing in place are not uniform. The living environment (urban, rural, or suburban) is critical in shaping how older adults engage with their surroundings, maintain independence, and participate socially. Every setting offers unique opportunities and challenges for ageing populations. Opting for a place-sensitive approach that accounts for these diverse experiences, researchers, policymakers, and practitioners can create environments that support ageing in place for all older adults, fostering security, comfort, and connectedness throughout the ageing process.

Inclusive Decision-Making Processes

Many of the case studies presented in this paper highlight the value of participatory methods in involving and sometimes empowering older adults to play an active role in local decision-making processes. These participatory approaches offer a pathway for usually marginalised groups, such as older migrants, older women, or older adults with disabilities, to voice their unique concerns and needs. Ensuring the inclusion of diverse groups in research projects, policies and programs, the participatory process enables a wide range of experiences and perspectives to be heard and considered. Future research should continue to explore the ways of refinement, and expansion of these methods to include even more nuanced forms of participation, ensuring no voices are left out of the debates and discussions.

Hearing the Voices of Unrepresented

The WG2's work overarching topic refers to the significance of enhancing the voice of those often underrepresented or overlooked in research programmes and society, in general. These include Indigenous communities, older people from migrant backgrounds, people with disabilities, those living in rural or remote areas and individuals lacking access to infrastructure and services. The inclusion of these voices allows for a more comprehensive understanding of the diverse experiences and situations of older adults. Moreover, it leads to the creation of more inclusive policies, services, and research agendas. Actively seeking out these perspectives ensures that future initiatives are equitable and better tailored to the needs of all older adults, regardless of their background, social or economic capital, or geographic location.

Recognising Intersectionality

The successful involvement of older populations in research, policy development, and service design requires a deep understanding of the intersectionality inherent within this demographic. Older adults form a particularly heterogeneous group; their life and ageing experiences are shaped by a multitude of aspects, including age, gender, ethnicity, religion, nationality, sexual orientation, education, socioeconomic status, and more. Recognising this complexity is essential to addressing the unique needs and challenges that arise from these overlapping identities. For instance, older women from migrant backgrounds may face distinct challenges in accessing healthcare or social services compared to their male or native-born counterparts. Incorporating intersectionality into research design and policy-making ensures that solutions address the specific needs of these diverse subgroups.

Future Research Directions

Based on the foregoing conclusions, it is advisable to briefly examine a few significant research directions. These may stimulate the reflections of readers of this White Paper but also serve as a basis for discussion for future work by members of WG2.

Firstly, we should examine how to mobilise local communities better, including informal networks, neighbourhood groups and local governments, to support the social inclusion of older people. This research could explore strategies for fostering stronger ties between older adults and their communities, particularly for those marginalised or live in isolated environments. The emphasis here would be on how the community can act as a buffer against isolation and social exclusion.

Then, identify how researchers and practitioners can be more sensitive to intersectionality when designing and conducting participatory projects with older people. This research could focus on developing more inclusive methodologies that account for the multiple layers of identity (age, gender, cultural backgrounds, etc.) that shape older adults' experiences and needs. That may involve exploring new ways to engage individuals who face multiple forms of discrimination or exclusion.

Moreover, it seems crucial to explore the factors leading to more inclusion in research, service provision programmes and public policies. What are the core elements contributing to the success of inclusive policies and programs for older adults? Studying successful examples allows us to identify the factors - such as accessibility, more cultural and local control of resources, and sustainability - that make programmes more effective in meeting the needs of diverse older populations. We should also investigate how to ensure that these initiatives reach marginalised groups.

Furthermore, it is worth considering how can we utilise digital tools and platforms to increase the social inclusion and participation of older people, especially those with limited mobility, living in remote or marginalised areas. Collaborating with Working Group 1 “Health, Care and Support”, and Working Group 3 “Technology and Innovation” research in this area could explore the potential of technologies - such as virtual communities, telehealth services and online participatory platforms - to provide opportunities for engagement, reduce social isolation and improve access to services for older people who face geographical or mobility limitations.

In conclusion, the research and projects presented in this paper collectively emphasise the transformative potential of participatory approaches and community involvement in improving the lives of older adults. Prioritising inclusivity, cultural relevance, and active engagement enables these initiatives to provide valuable insights into creating supportive and empowering environments for ageing populations. Future research and policy development should continue to build on these conclusions, ensuring meeting the diverse needs of older adults through collaborative efforts.

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